

Mixed β -Diketonates of Copper(II) and Their Base Adducts

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$\text{Cu}(\text{bzac})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{dbm})_2$ were reacted with an equimolar proportion of a number of other copper(II) β -diketonates ($\text{Cu L}'$), where $\text{L}' = \text{dpm, hfac, tfac, tta}$ or pta in dichloromethane, and mixed β -diketonates of the type ($\text{Cu LL}'$), where $\text{L} = \text{bzac}$ or dbm , were isolated. Some of these mixed β -diketonates were reacted with pyridine to produce penta and hexacoordinated base adducts. These were characterised on the basis of analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, and infrared and electronic spectral data.

THE chemistry of metal β -diketonates has aroused considerable recent interest¹ in such diverse areas as spectral studies, gas chromatography, solvent extractions², column and thin layer chromatography, nmr shift reagents, laser technology and as initiators in polymerisation reactions. Bis(β -diketonato) metal(II) complexes behave as Lewis acids and form five- or six-coordinate adducts with neutral donor molecules⁴. Stability of an adduct depends both on the basicity of the β -diketonate and on that of neutral ligand. Introduction of an electron withdrawing group, such as CF_3^- into β -diketonate increases the affinity of central metal ion for ligation⁵. As a part of general programme on the reactions of transition metal β -diketonates, C^{δ} and C^{δ} bonded β -diketonates and complexes having β -diketonates as counter ions have been reported⁶⁻⁹. Also, C^{δ} -bonded hetero- β -diketonates have been reported¹⁰ showing the lability of the C^{δ} -bonded acetylacetonato moiety.

In continuation of this work, the present communication describes the mixed β -diketonates of copper(II) and their base adducts formed by reacting equimolar proportion of different copper(II) β -diketonates.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Different copper(II) β -diketonates were prepared from copper(II) acetate by earlier reported methods^{11,12}. Equimolar mixture of $\text{Cu}(\text{bzac})_2$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{dbm})_2$ and other copper(II) β -diketonates, *i.e.* $\text{Cu}(\text{hfac})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{tfac})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{tta})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{pta})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{dpm})_2$ were dissolved in 20 ml of dichloromethane and stirred magnetically at 40° for 20-30 min. Volume of the solutions were concentrated to 5 ml by a rotary vacuum evaporator and the samples were crystallised on slow cooling. The crystals were filtered, washed with small amount of ether and dried in vacuum. Copper was estimated iodometrically to determine the composition. The mixed β -diketonates were suspended in 3 ml pyridine and stirred magnetically

for 20 min at 50-60°. The solutions were kept in refrigerator overnight and the crystalline compounds so obtained were filtered and dried in vacuum desiccator containing liquid paraffin. Copper and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods.

Conductance was measured in acetone solution (0.001 M) of the complexes using Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimens at room temperature by Gouy method. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 and 337 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded in dichloromethane solution (0.01 M) of the complexes using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and the spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The complexes have the general composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{L}')]_2$, where L is bzac or dbm and L' is hfac, tfac, tta, pta or dpm, and the base adducts have the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{L}')\text{py}_2]_2$ or $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{L}')(\text{py})]_2$ (Table 1). These are green, olive green or blue crystalline solids having fairly low melting points and are soluble in common organic solvents, like ethanol, methanol, acetone, benzene, chloroform and dichloromethane. Acetone solution (0.001 M) of the complexes have low molar conductance values indicating non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment of the complexes indicate them to be paramagnetic with the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for the copper(II) ion. The base adducts of the mixed chelates are fairly stable in air unlike the adducts of bis(acetylacetonato)-copper(II) which loses the base on exposure to air.

Important infrared bands have been assigned and are listed in Table 2. Ir spectra of the mixed chelates and adducts do not exhibit any band due to free carbonyl group and also of free pyridine in the base adducts. There are two distinct sets of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ bands assignable¹³ to L and L' β -diketonate

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF MIXED β -DIKETONATES

Sl. no.	Compounds	Colour/form	M.p. °C	ΔM $\Omega^{-1}cm^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
						Cu	N
1.	Cu(bzac)(hfac)	Green/cryst.	132	8.5	1.81	14.95 (14.7)	—
2.	Cu(bzac)(tfac)	Blue/cryst.	115	6.2	1.79	16.5 (16.8)	—
3.	Cu(bzac)(tta)	Green/cryst.	198	10.1	1.82	14.56 (14.3)	—
4.	Cu(bzac)(pta)	Blue/cryst.	148	9.4	1.82	15.45 (15.15)	—
5.	Cu(bzac)(dpm)	Blue/cryst.	131	7.6	1.83	15.32 (15.6)	—
6.	Cu(dbm)(hfac)	Peagreen/cryst.	171	8.2	1.79	12.61 (12.87)	—
7.	Cu(dbm)(tfac)	Leaf green/cryst.	164	8.5	1.79	14.72 (14.46)	—
8.	Cu(dbm)(tta)	Green/cryst.	197	9.8	1.81	12.8 (12.52)	—
9.	Cu(dbm)(pta)	Olivegreen/cryst.	97	7.6	1.81	13.6 (13.2)	—
10.	Cu(dpm)(bzac)	Leafgreen/cryst.	218	9.4	1.80	13.9 (14.2)	—
11.	Cu(bzac)(hfac)py ₂	Green/needles	120	8.6	1.82	10.52 (10.77)	4.42 (4.74)
12.	Cu(bzac)(tfac)py ₂	Green/flakes	135	8.2	1.83	11.48 (11.86)	5.36 (5.22)
13.	Cu(dbm)(hfac)py ₂	Green/crystal	158	7.8	1.81	9.44 (9.75)	4.38 (4.29)
14.	Cu(dbm)(tfac)py ₂	Green/plates	142	8.8	1.82	10.82 (10.63)	4.41 (4.68)
15.	Cu(bzac)(dpm)py	Green/needles	146	9.8	1.83	13.31 (13.05)	2.66 (2.87)
16.	Cu(bzac)(tta)py	Green/crystal	156	6.5	1.82	12.35 (12.11)	2.54 (2.66)

bzac = anion of benzoylacetone, dbm = anion of dibenzoylmethane, dpm = anion of dipivaloylmethane, hfac = anion of hexafluoroacetylacetone, tfac = anion of trifluoroacetylacetone, tta = anion of thenoyltrifluoroacetone, pta = anion of pivaloyltrifluoroacetone.

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Ir spectra (cm ⁻¹)			ν pyridine ring	Electronic spectra (nm) λ_{max} (ϵ)
	$\nu_{C=O}$	L'	ν_{Cu-O}		
1.	1580	1640	420	—	650 (35)
2.	1580	1615	425	—	650 (30)
3.	1585	1605	420	—	655 (30)
4.	1585	1610	430	—	650 (35)
5.	1580	1590	425	—	660 (35)
6.	1600	1630	420	—	660 (35)
7.	1605	1615	420	—	655 (30)
8.	1600	1605	425	—	650 (30)
9.	1600	1610	430	—	660 (35)
10.	1600	1580	430	—	660 (35)
11.	1600	1660	380	640	650 (50)
12.	1600	1625	385	645	650 (50)
13.	1610	1655	380	640	660 (55)
14.	1610	1625	390	635	655 (55)
15.	1600	1605	390	640	650 (80)
16.	1600	1620	380	645	655 (85)

moieties. Compared to the free β -diketones $\nu_{C=O}$ bands have been observed at considerably lower frequency regions in the mixed chelates. In the base adducts $\nu_{C=O}$ bands have shifted to the higher frequency region on coordination with the base¹⁴,

pyridine. Metal-oxygen stretching bands were assigned on the basis of the observations by Thornton *et al.*^{15,16}. There are actually five metal sensitive bands in the far-infrared region. The least coupled M-O stretching band, ν_{Cu-O} was taken in this case as it shifts much on coordinations of the nitrogen ligand. In case of complexes under investigations ν_{Cu-O} shifts around 35-45 cm⁻¹ to the lower frequency region in the base adducts compared to the parent mixed chelates and are observed at 380-390 cm⁻¹. Usually ν_{M-O} shifts to lower frequency in the base adducts, but this shift is quite large in case of copper(II) β -diketonates. This large decrease may be due to the repulsion effect and Jahn-Teller distortion taken together¹⁷. There are a number of bands in the far-infrared region for which it was difficult to assign ν_{Cu-N} in the base adducts. However, pyridine has the characteristic band at 605 cm⁻¹ due to ring vibration (inplane ring deformation mode) and this band is much sensitive to coordinations and shifts to higher frequency region¹⁸. In the present case, the base adducts exhibit this band around 640-645 cm⁻¹ region indicating coordination of pyridine.

Visible electronic spectra of the mixed chelates and the base adducts have been studied in dichloromethane solution. The mixed chelates give a broad absorption band at 650-660 nm with an ϵ value of 30-35. In case of the base adducts the band maxima does not shift much, but there is an increase in the intensity of the absorption band. In case of the bis-pyridine adducts ϵ values are around 50-55 whereas the monopyridine adducts have a very high in ϵ value, around 80-85. Graddon⁴ and Walker¹⁹ have observed^{4,19-21} that in case of the base adducts an increase in the intensity of absorption band occurs without much shifting of the band maxima. To see that the monoadducts are truly 5-coordinated monomers rather than 6-coordinated dimers, the molecular weight of the compound [Cu(bzac)(dpm)py] was determined by vapour phase osmometric method in benzene. The observed molecular weight is 465.6 as compared with the calculated one, 486.54. This shows that the monoadducts are penta coordinated and bis-adducts are hexacoordinated.

Adducts of these copper(II) mixed β -diketonates are much stable than the adducts of bis(acetylacetonato)copper(II). This is obvious because when CH_3 group in acetylacetonone is replaced by electron withdrawing group, the stability of the chelates decreases, at the same time however, the decrease of electron density around the central Cu^{2+} ion enhances its ability to form adducts. Formation of the mixed β -diketonates indicates the lability of the copper(II) β -diketonates.

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